

AI4Deliberation

Systematic Literature Review outputs

03/2025

Public

Search algorithm handed to the contributors:

Step 1: Search for each search term in the selected databases.

Step 2: Review the top 100 studies, ranked by citation count returned per keyword for fit.

Step 3: Include studies relevant to the questions associated with your task.

Step 4: Check for study in shared Zotero Library -> if already there, tag with your task label -> if not upload and tag for task.

Step 5: Check references of all studies identified by your search for further relevant literature -> add if not already referenced by your search.

Step 6: Document details for each study in shared excel file "Sheet: Studies".

Step 7: Collect and aggregate information to comply with PRISMA standard reporting.

Leading questions per section:

Section	Details
Digital Platforms and Democratic Theory	<p>Q1: What are normatively developed foundations for successful deliberation?</p> <p>Q2: What are empirical metrics for successful deliberation?</p> <p>Q3: What are normatively developed design principles for successful deliberation on digital platforms?</p> <p>Q4: What are empirical metrics for successful deliberation on digital platforms?</p>
Affordances and Drawbacks of Digital Deliberation	<p>Q1: What are specific problems of deliberation as a concept that digital deliberation can address?</p> <p>Q2: What are specific affordances of deliberation platforms for deliberation, theoretically speaking?</p> <p>Q3: What are specific affordances of deliberation platforms for deliberation, actually implemented?</p> <p>Q4: Are specific affordances of deliberation platforms evaluated toward their contributions?</p>
Deliberation Formats	<p>Q1: What are specific formats of deliberation mentioned [Face 2 Face and mediated]?</p> <p>Q2: What are specific benefits of these formats regarding deliberation?</p> <p>Q3: What are specific drawbacks of these formats regarding deliberation?</p>

	Q4: Are benefits and drawbacks empirically tested or is there other kind of evidence presented?
Platform Features and Differentiation	<p>Q1: What are different platforms available for digitally mediated deliberation?</p> <p>Q2: What type and format of deliberation does the platform offer?</p> <p>Q3: What specific affordances does the platform offer?</p> <p>Q4: Who is the provider of the platform?</p> <p>Q5: Who is using the platform for which use case?</p> <p>Q6: Is there an evidence-based evaluation available?</p>
AI Features	<p>Q1: Are there specific AI use cases for deliberation proposed (speculative, conceptual)?</p> <p>Q2: Are there specific AI use cases for deliberation discussed (specific examples)?</p> <p>Q3: What are the specific affordances of AI for deliberation?</p> <p>Q4: What are specific risks of AI for deliberation?</p>
Argumentation Mining	<p>Q1: What approaches to argumentation mining are available in principle?</p> <p>Q2: What specific approaches to argumentation mining are already used in deliberation platforms?</p> <p>Q3: Please list approaches in use, their specific task, and the platform they are used in.</p> <p>Q4: How is the performance of these approaches measured?</p>
Evaluation Models	<p>Q1: What are approaches to the evaluation of the quality of the results of digitally mediated deliberation?</p> <p>Q2: What are approaches to the evaluation of the quality of the deliberative experience in digitally mediated deliberation?</p> <p>Q3: What are approaches to the</p>

	<p>evaluation of the quality of the technology in digitally mediated deliberation?</p> <p>Q4: Are there other topics of evaluation in digitally mediated deliberation?</p>
Frameworks for Institutionalization	<p>Q1: Is there a framework for the institutionalization of deliberative practices or platforms?</p> <p>Q2: What is the role of design, maintenance, conduct, and follow-up in these frameworks?</p> <p>Q3: What other elements of institutionalized deliberation are mentioned?</p>
Best Practices	<p>Q1: Does the paper propose best practices for designing digitally mediated deliberation?</p> <p>Q2: Does the paper propose best practices for the conduct of digitally mediated deliberation?</p> <p>Q3: Does the paper propose best practices for the use of AI in digital deliberation platforms?</p>

Overall Prisma Statement:

Template from: Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71

Conceptual Map:

The concept map summarizes the key findings for each chapter and draws connections between the individual findings across the chapters:

Link: <https://debategraph.org/Stream.aspx?nid=731860&vt=ngraph&dc=all>

